

Data Management Plan

WP8 Y2Q4

Task leader: Consoft Sistemi

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Introduction

The objectives of the task 8.3 “Data and knowledge management policies & quality assurance” will be to guarantee the respect of the data and knowledge management policies encouraging achievement of the highest result in term of quality of result and internal procedures. This task will manage also ethical issues linked to patient privacy, data protection and informed consent issues. Similarly, this task will define rules for sharing of project data and findings to the scientific community for further exploitation (it is meaningful to recall that DECI adheres to the European Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020).

This document is intended to be a living document that will be updated, if needed, according to the needs during the life of the Project. For this reason, some sections will be filled with necessary information developed during DECI future steps. Even the already documented parts can be subject to enhancement.

This document is an internal management instrument. It is released as a Project Deliverable, under confidentiality; in order to ease tracking of Project progress against stated objectives, and to track easily changes in the Project together with the related motivations.

This document should always be considered jointly with the General Agreement, the Description of the Work and the Consortium Agreement

For the ethics issues a valuable role will be played by the Scientific Advisory Board, leveraging the experience in European and national regulatory frameworks and in other research project of prominent members, at strategic level, of consortium organizations and health organizations, which have endorsed the project.

In particular, this evolving document describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by DECI research project.

This is a document outlining how research data will be handled during a research project, and even after the project is completed, describing what data will be collected, processed or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

Key points:

1. **Description of data sets produced** within the DECI project and the agreed procedures for **management, sharing, archiving and preservation of each data set**;
2. **Identification of the key ethical and legal issues** that need to be addressed through the project and in the project’s ethics guideline.
3. **Research participation:** autonomy, privacy, dignity, safety aspects; informed consent process.

4. **Publication policy:** importance of publishing work that is not only successful in this area as it will be beneficial for others doing similar research; also important as the area is so new that mistakes will not be reproduced.

The document content is divided in the following main sections:

1. **Data sets,** describing all the data sets created during the project lifetime, the various standards and metadata, the resources used to produce the various data sets, policies regarding data sharing and open access policies, containing a description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, dissemination actions, software and other tools and open data specifications.
2. **Security:** description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data.
3. **Ethics:** description of the procedures that will be put in place to preserve people private data.

Two appendices close the document and include the Ethical Issues Questionnaire and a list of documents to be submitted to Ethical Committees.

1 DECI data sets: standards, sharing, archiving and preservation

The principal set of data that DECI project will produce are the following:

1. Data of patients, doctors, patients' relatives
2. Data related to patient activity
 - Raw data collected from the wearable and sent to DECI platform
 - Data obtained by processing raw data by means of proprietary algorithms
3. Data related to the work of partners (deliverables, articles, and tools)

Following the guidelines provided in the document *Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020* for each dataset defined above the following template will be applied:

Section Name	Description
Data set reference and name	Identifier for the data set to be produced.
Data set description	Description of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin (in case it is collected), nature and scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse.
Standards and metadata	Reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created.
Data sharing	Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

Table 1 Data set

Some common problems related to ethics, security and statistical analysis on private data collected during DECI project will be addressed in dedicated sections.

The management of the data sets involved in DECI project can be summarized in the following picture:

Figure 1 Data set storage and flows

The public data set (paragraph 1.4 Deliverables, articles and tools dataset) will be published in open access on DECI project website for at least 3 years after the end of the project.

The FONDAZIONE POLITECNICO DI MILANO (FPM) established in PIAZZA LEONARDO DA VINCI 32, MILANO 20133, Italy will have the responsibility of the data on DECI project website.

The public deliverables can be also stored on the public repository OpenAIRE.

Since it is expected that an instance of the DECI platform will be installed in each pilot site, the private data sets (paragraph 1.1 Patients, professionals, patients' relatives dataset; paragraph 1.2 Wearable dataset; paragraph 1.3 Patients activity dataset) will be stored on the respective site datacenter that will also be in charge of the storage costs and take responsibility for backups and security.

The responsibility of private datasets belongs to the four pilot sites:

- Italian Pilot - FONDAZIONE DON CARLO GNOCCHI ONLUS (FONDAZIONE DON CARLO GNOCCHI ONLUS) established in PIAZZALE RODOLFO MORANDI 6, MILANO 20121, Italy;

- Israeli Pilot - MACCABI HEALTHCARE SERVICES (MACCABI) established in HAMERED STREET 27, TEL AVIV 68125, Israel;
- Swedish Pilot - VASTRA GOTALANDS LANS LANDSTING (VGR), established in REGIONENS HUS, VANERSBORG 462 80, Sweden;
- Spanish Pilot - SERVICIO MADRILENO DE SALUD (SERMAS) established in PLAZA CARLOS TRIAS BERTRAN 7, MADRID 28020, Spain.

As the data are private they won't be shared outside the site, but their anonymized and aggregated form will be shared inside the consortium upon approval of the ethical committee for statistical purposes (e.g. KPIs evaluation). For evaluation purposes, patient data will be anonymized and shared with the designated partners of the Consortium (CHI, FPM and RRD) that will be responsible for outcomes evaluation.

A detailed description of the involved data sets, sharing and storage policies can be found in the next chapters.

1.1 Data of patients, professionals, patients' relatives

Data Set Reference and Name

Patients, professionals, patients' relatives dataset

1.1.1 Data set description

The data related to patients involved into DECI project are collected into the platform. Patients data required from DECI platform are grouped by Area and could be summarized in the following table:

Area	Data
Demographic	Marital status
	Last Name
	First Name
	ID number
	Gender
	Date of birth
	Primary phone
	Secondary phone
	Email
	Address
	Height
	Weight
	BMI (Body Max Index)
	MNA (Mininutritional Assessment-short form)
	informal caregiver First Name
	informal caregiver Last Name
Country code	

	Clinical Site code
	Informal caregiver's birth date
Medical	Physician/Case manager name (and specialization, if required)
	Operator/Coordinator name
	Main Disease
	Comorbidity
	Other disease
	Planned visit
	Unplanned visit
	Planned call
	Unplanned call
	Team meeting
	Clinical questionnaires data with total scores, question's score and thresholds question values
Photo	Photo
Contacts	Patient's contacts
	Relative's contacts

Table 2 Patient's data required from the DECI platform

To standardize the clinical information between clinical partners, a minimum set of instruments (tests, scales, questionnaires) called MDS (DECI Minimum Data Set) is introduced.

Domain	Test
Cognition	Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE)
	Clock Drawing Test (CDT)
Staging	MoCa (in Israel)
Functionality	Basic ADL (BADL)
	Instrumental ADL (IADL)
	EuroQL-5D-5L
Caregiver	Zarit Burden Interview (for Caregiver)
Data Gathering	Additional demographic data of the patient
	Additional demographic data of the informal caregiver (family)
	Physical exercise
	Cognitive exercise

Table 3 Minimum data set of instrument

Regarding professionals' data, the integration platform holds the Doctor/Nurse's name only. If required, it is possible for the name to hold the Doctor's area of expertise too. The integration platform will manage also questionnaires scores and the related alerts to professionals' (if requested).

1.1.2 Standard and metadata

To collect the clinical information used in DECI Minimum Data Set (MDS) about older person's needs the following standards were used:

- Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a 30-points cognitive test widely used in clinical and research settings to measure cognitive impairment;
- Clock Drawing Test (CDT), a brief cognitive task to assess global cognitive dysfunctions;
- MoCa – will be used in Israel site for inclusion
- Autonomy in the Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL), a questionnaire to assess the patient ability to perform complex activities (e.g. managing money, preparing meals);
- Autonomy in the basic Activities of Daily Living (BADL) a questionnaire to assess the patient ability to perform basic activities (e.g. dressing, self-feeding).

Extra tools for assessment of different perspectives during evaluation are:

- EuroQL-5D-5L is a questionnaire that assesses patient's perceived quality of life;
- Zarit Burden Interview instrument evaluates perceived burden felt by an informal caregiver.

1.1.3 Data sharing

The data described above are sensible data of patients so they will be collected at site level and won't be shared outside of it (even at the consortium) for ethical reasons (please refer to **ethics chapter**).

However these data can be collected and aggregated in their anonymized form from each pilot site for statistical reasons (e.g. KPIs evaluation) and shared inside the consortium under ethical committee approval. To avoid issues related to privacy and ethics, the data are treated so that will be impossible to identify the individual patient.

1.1.4 Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)

An instance of the DECI platform will be installed in each pilot site organization and it will be compliant with the organizational ICT and security system for each country. The data will be stored in the ICT infrastructure of the hospital, so the choice of the storage type (cloud or internal datacenter) as well the backup procedures and security handling will be demanded to each site depending from their needs and rules.

The expected storage size for the above data, taking in account that the number of patients for each site is roughly 200 people is estimated as 1 GB.

Data will be stored until the end of the project in each site. The decision to keep the data afterwards this period, how and where, will be demanded to the ethical committee of each pilot.

1.2 Data related to patient activity: raw data collected from the wearable

Dataset reference and name

Wearable Dataset

1.2.1 Dataset description

The data contained into this dataset are produced by the wearable device that is designed to transmit activity monitoring information each 10 minutes. Asynchronous transmission is also possible using the main button on the watch.

The following parameters are stored inside DECI platform:

Parameter Name	Description
Client	Defines the JSON structure
Packet type	Defines the packet type
sender id	Unique id of the transmitting watch
Battery voltage	Transmitting watch battery level
RSSI	Received radio signal strength
Step counter	Cumulative step counter
Fall counter	Cumulative fall event counter
Mobility index	Mean value of the mobility index of the last 10 minutes
From very low to very hight mobility counter	Very low/low/medium/high/very high mobility counter
base Id	Base station IMEI code

Table 4 Data produced by the wearable

1.2.2 Standards and metadata

Data transfer between wearable and home gateway is transferred over the 869.22 Mhz frequency band, using a proprietary radio transmission protocol, to ensure energy management. Data is encrypted and encoded using the “Idea” algorithm to ensure security and CRC computation on the payload is employed to assure data integrity. Data is transferred from the home gateway to the DECI Platform by means of a secure transmission over TCP socket server.

The base station parses incoming data from the watch and creates a standard JSON data packet. The home gateway opens a TCP socket to the socket server running on the DECI Platform. The TCP socket is created upon the GPRS network. Concerning the air link, the 2G GSM/GPRS security and integrity features are exploited. This mobile network link is established towards an APN. A secure APN shall be used, allowing only connection from a specific set of SIM cards. From the APN to the socket server a VPN network is employed to ensure data security. The TCP socket server accepts only data from the secure APN. To even improve data payload security and integrity, the JSON packet contains a CRC and it is encrypted with a proprietary algorithm.

1.2.3 Data sharing

The data described above are sensible data of patient activity so they will be collected at site level and won't be shared outside of it (even at the consortium) for ethical reasons (please refer to **ethics chapter**).

However these data can be collected and aggregated in their anonymized form from each pilot site for statistical reasons (e.g. KPIs evaluation) and shared inside the consortium under ethical committee approval. To avoid issues related to privacy and ethics, the data are treated so that will be impossible to identify the individual patient.

1.2.4 Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)

An instance of the DECI platform will be installed in each pilot site organization and it will be compliant with the organizational ICT and security system for each country. The data will be stored in the ICT infrastructure of the hospital, so the choice of the storage type (cloud or internal datacenter) as well the backup procedures and security handling will be demanded to each site depending from their needs and rules.

The expected storage size for the above data, taking in account that the number of patients for each site is roughly 200 people and the data are sent from the wearable every 10 minutes is estimated as 8 GB/year.

Data will be stored for at least next five years (estimated data size 40 GB).

The data will be kept on each site during the project. The decision to keep the data afterwards this period, how and where, will be demanded to the ethical committee of each pilot.

1.3 Data related to patient activity obtained by processing raw data by means of proprietary algorithms

Dataset reference and name

Patients Activity Dataset

1.3.1 Dataset description

Raw Data produced from the wearable are stored inside the platform and then processed by means of internal and proprietary algorithms taking in account data from patients (weight, height, gender, age). By elaborating the raw data the algorithms produce different records for each patient that can be exported in CSV and PDF format for statistical purposes without sensible information about the patient:

- Calories consumption;
- Steps number;
- Average speed;
- Traveled distance;
- Mobility index.

1.3.2 Standards and metadata

All the data referenced by the algorithms are expressed following the SI (Système International d'Unités) such as kg for weight, cm for height and so on. The derived data can be exported in PDF and CSV formats.

1.3.3 Data sharing

These data can be collected and aggregated in their anonymized form from each pilot site for statistical reasons (e.g. KPIs evaluation) and shared inside the consortium under ethical committee approval. To avoid issues related to privacy and ethics, the data are treated so that will be impossible to identify the individual patient.

1.3.4 Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)

An instance of the DECI platform will be installed in each pilot site organization and it will be compliant with the organizational ICT and security system for each country. The data will be stored in the ICT infrastructure of the hospital, so the choice of the storage type (cloud or internal datacenter) as well the backup procedures and security handling will be demanded to each site depending from their needs and rules. The data will be kept on each site for at least 3 years from the end of the project. The decision to keep the data afterwards this period, how and where, will be demanded to the ethical committee of each pilot.

1.4 Data related to the work of partners (deliverables, articles and tools)

Data Set Reference and Name

Deliverable dataset

Homepage: <http://deci-europe.eu>

1.4.1 Dataset Description

The DECI project activities have been divided in Work Packages (WPs) allowing parallel execution and overall coordination according to common specifications. Each WP is divided into tasks that are described in one or more deliverables that will be developed via joint efforts from all partners involved in the relative Work Packages.

All produced deliverables are linked each other and focused on different targets that depends on the WP content. They describe different aspects and issues starting from the analysis of existing models for managing MCI/MD population and of their needs, the design, implementation and pilot validation of ICT solutions for digital services, finally the financial and administrative coordination on project activities.

The dataset is useful to understand the main aims of DECI Projects, the benchmark results, the pilot scenarios and the main involved actors.

1.4.2 Standard and metadata

Standard

Technical deliverables concerning the system design consist of a top-down strategy. Standards such as UML uses case and scenario descriptions are used for the services and procedures implementation.

Metadata

For public deliverables that will be uploaded to the OpenAIRE repository, a metadata schema will be available according the OpenAIRE metadata guidelines.

1.4.3 Data sharing

Repository

All deliverables will be available during the project and for 3 years after the end of the project at <http://deci-europe.eu>, following the dissemination level agreed among partners and reported in the following table. Public deliverables can be also uploaded on the OpenAIRE repository.

Openness

The following is the list of deliverables, documents, web-tools, scientific publications that the DECI partner will produce during the whole EU project. For each deliverable there is

the indication about the type of data, the dissemination level (**DL**) that can be public (**PU**) or confidential restricted (**CO**) only for member of the consortium.

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Type	DL
D1.1	State-of-the-art of clinical and assistance management models and practices of elderly patients with MCI	WP1	Report	PU
D1.2	Patient clusters	WP1	Report	PU
D1.3	Patients, caregivers and support and clinical organisational needs	WP1	Report	PU
D1.4	Key performance indicator to be monitored	WP1	Report	PU
D1.5	Design of the final pilot based on the pre pilot study	WP1	Demonstrator	CO
D2.1	Benchmarking of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments	WP2	Report	PU
D2.2	Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments	WP2	Report	PU
D2.3	Change management and introduction processes of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments	WP2	Report	PU
D3.1	Document describing the designed business model, the process with details on the procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions	WP3	Demonstrator	PU
D3.2	Document of ICT solution requirements analysis	WP3	Report	CO
D3.3	Document of definition of overall application (ICT solution and processes) in each country	WP3	Demonstrator	CO
D3.4	Guidelines for the implementation of the IT solution and identification of types of intervention necessary for the proper introduction	WP3	Report	CO

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Type	DL
	of the solution into operational processes			
D4.1	Living and Home automation (technical report)	WP4	Other	CO
D4.2	Application layer (technical report)	WP4	Other	CO
D4.3	Integration of the ICT platform: main architecture, hosting and interfaces to external system (technical report)	WP4	Other	CO
D4.4	Validation and test reports	WP4	Other	CO
D5.1	Report on application of business model, processes and ICT tools in Italy	WP5	Demonstrator	CO
D5.2	Report on application of business model, processes and ICT tools in Sweden	WP5	Demonstrator	CO
D5.3	Report on application of business model, processes and ICT tools in Spain	WP5	Demonstrator	CO
D5.4	Report on application of business model, processes and ICT tools in Israel	WP5	Demonstrator	CO
D6.1	Report on assessment methods and results	WP6	Report	PU
D6.2	A business case	WP6	Report	PU
D6.3	Exploitation plan	WP6	Report	CO
D7.1	IPR Protection	WP7	Report	CO
D7.2	Dissemination Plan	WP7	Report	CO
D7.3	Report on dissemination and exploitation activities	WP7	Report	CO
D8.1	Project management plan	WP8	Report	CO
D8.2	Yearly report on the project progress and status - 1st	WP8	Report	CO
D8.3	Yearly report on the project progress and status - 2nd	WP8	Report	CO
D8.4	Yearly report on the project progress and status - 3rd	WP8	Report	CO

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Type	DL
D8.5	Data Management Plan	WP8	Report	PU
D8.6	Final report of the implemented actions and results	WP8	Report	CO

Table 5 Deliverables dissemination level

License

The open access deliverables are released under the Creative Common CC by 2.5 license.

Social

Repository references as well as some public documents will be shared on social networks such as LinkedIn and Twitter on the official account of DECI project.

1.4.4 Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)

Preservation

All the data described in the above table will be stored in the DECI datacenter located in Corso Svizzera 185 - 10149, Torino.

The datacenter is isolated and managed by ISO 27001 policies with the access, intrusion, fire control, business continuity and climate.

The data will be stored in DECI website for 3 years after the end of the project. Regarding the public deliverables stored in OpenAIRE public open access repository, their availability depend on OpenAIRE policies.

Backup

The datacenter handles differential backups to a virtual level (VM) weekly, with monthly retention and possibility of recovery within 30 minutes.

2 Security: data protection issues

DECI project will not deal with 'EU-classified information' as background or results.

As a common rule, all partners will be committed to protecting the privacy of users by keeping all data collected on a secure server.

One possibility to do so in the project is not to use participants' names, they will be given codes in all communication in the project. Additionally, the informed consent procedure will explicitly address the questions of recordings of any kind and permission of users will be asked for their use.

Another option is to install the system in each pilot organization and allow the organizational security system to work with the system.

The options will be discussed to achieve the best possible results.

Trust in the DECI system is a complex and important issue. The system developers, when working with users, will assess what contributes to trust and now is users' trust in the system maintained.

2.1 Ownership of results and ownership transfer

Results achieved during Project duration or as an effect of the Project are owned by the Party that generated them. The Party has faculty to decide whether or how to protect results.

In case of joint ownership, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the priori consent of the other joint owners.

Each of the joint owners shall be entitles to otherwise exploit the jointly owned results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties, if the other joint owners are given:

1. At least 45 calendar days notice;
2. Fair and reasonable compensation.

Each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results. Each Party may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its Results to. The other Parties hereby waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to a transfer to listed third parties. The transferring Party shall inform the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties will not be affected by such transfer.

The Parties recognize that in the framework of a merger or an acquisition of an important part of its assets, it may be impossible under applicable EU and national laws on mergers and acquisitions for a Party to give the full 45 calendar days prior notice for the transfer as foreseen in the Grant Agreement.

The obligations above apply only for as long as other Parties still have - or still may request - Access Rights to the Results.

2.2 Dissemination of results and access rights

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after it ends, the dissemination of own Results shall ensure that prior notice of any planned publication is given at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice.

An objection is justified if:

1. The protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected;
2. The objecting Party's legitimate academic or commercial interests in relation to the Results or Background would be significantly harmed.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. The involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the objection on a timely basis; objecting Party shall

not unreasonably continue the opposition. The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time of the objection

Each Party shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the Project do not knowingly infringe third party property rights.

Any Access Rights granted expressly exclude any rights to sublicense unless expressly stated otherwise. Access Rights shall be free of any administrative transfer costs. Access Rights are granted on a non-exclusive basis.

The granting of Access Rights may be made conditional on the acceptance of specific conditions aimed at ensuring that these rights will be used only for the intended purpose and that appropriate confidentiality obligations are in place,

Access Rights to Results and Background Needed for the performance of the own work of a Party shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

Access Rights to Results needed for exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions. Access rights to Results for internal research activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis. Access Rights to Background if needed for exploitation of a party's own Results, including for research on behalf of a third party, shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions. A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

2.3 Non-disclosure of information

All information disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to any other Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been marked as "confidential", is considered "Confidential Information".

The Recipients undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment of non-disclosure, for a period of 4 years after the end of the Project:

1. Not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
2. Not to disclose Confidential Information to any third party without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
3. To ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis;
4. To return to the Disclosing Party on demand all Confidential Information supplied to or acquired by the Recipients. The Recipients may keep a copy to archive or store Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations.

The Recipients shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the obligations on the part of their employees or third parties involved in the Project and shall ensure that they remain so

obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end of the Project and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party.

This shall not apply if the Recipient can show that:

1. The Confidential Information becomes publicly available;
2. The Confidential Information is no longer confidential;
3. The Confidential Information is transferred with no obligation of confidence;
4. The disclosure of the Confidential Information is foreseen by the GA;
5. The Confidential Information was independently developed by the Recipient;
6. The Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient;
7. The Recipient is required to disclose the Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations.

2.4 Health data protection

The DECI project involves data from healthcare organization as well as from other organizations and between professional care providers, patients and informal caregivers. The type of data coming from each actor has to be analyzed and the level of authorization and data protection issues as well as relevant ethical issues has to be defined.

All personal health data will be treated as “sensitive personal data” and the Directive to follow during the project will be the Directive 95/46/EC.

Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data of the Council of Europe of 1 January 1981 and the Declaration of Principles of the World Summit on the Information Society of 12 December 2003) will be followed as well.

As a result, the personal data of all citizens will have equivalent protection across the Union. In addition, Directive 2002/58/EC specifically deals with the protection of privacy in telecommunications. This Directive states that Member States must guarantee the confidentiality of communication through national regulations. This means that any unauthorized listening, tapping, storage or other kinds of interception of surveillance of communications is illegal. In particular:

1. Any person who requires access to sensitive information for the execution of his project activities must be expressly authorized and must declare to know, understand and correctly apply EU and national laws on security and privacy. Access to sensitive information will be enabled only if really necessary to the conduction of project activities;
2. The access control policies to the information systems and the methods of anonymization will be clearly defined and documented. The information will be made anonymous to allow for the identification and communication with volunteers should the need arise during or after the trial completes.
3. Clinical investigators will be subjected to correctly filling any documentation regarding the trial. They will be also responsible for patient privacy and critical data, being subjected to previously established regulations and to Good Clinical Practice (GCP) rules.

4. The unnecessary collection and use of personal data will be avoided;
5. Every source of the data will be clearly identified, describing whether it is collected as part of the research or is previously collected data being used, and checking it informed consents were properly collected.
6. About the issues described above, the partners will ensure that legality and privacy issues are properly addressed in the overall project and the Project Advisory Board will address ethical matters during the project.

In general terms, the appropriate data protection principles will be observed, including:

1. Data are fairly and lawfully processed
2. Data are used only in ways that are compatible with the original consent
3. The amount of data collected is relevant and not excessive
4. All reasonable efforts are taken to ensure data accuracy
5. The data are used in accordance with the rights of the study participant
6. The data are stored securely
7. The relevant international and national guidance will be consulted

Moreover, all European-based Partners will comply with the following laws and regulations:

1. The provisions of the current Harmonized Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice (ICHGCP E6)
2. The provisions of the current ISO 14155-1, 14155-2 (2003): Clinical Investigation of Medical Devices for Human Subjects, as well as regulations and guidelines published.
3. COMMISSION DIRECTIVE 2005/28/EC
4. Regulation EU No 536/2014 and EU and USA regulations require the protection of personal data (e.g. Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and HIPAA and to stay within the scope of informed consent.

All Partners will adhere to the aforementioned laws, regulations and practices. In addition, data protection issues in Israel and Sweden have to adhere to the following practices.

2.5 Data Protection Issues in Israel

Specifically addressing Israeli law, Maccabi will comply with IL regulations, including:

1. Section 7 in the Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty
2. Israeli Data Protection law (1981)
3. Patient's rights law (1996).

In general, the Israeli law and Ministry of Health (MOH) procedures that are in accordance with international procedures of ethical approvals and comply with European Directives.

1. In case of DBR patients, data are kept in a private cloud. When there is a request for research data, an application submitted to the Ethical Committee, which approve to get the relevant data under research question, go through the process of anonymity. These data are used only for research, and does request a signature on a consent form.
2. In case of clinical trial- A clinical trial involving human subjects shall not be conducted unless the Investigator has received informed consent from the clinical trial participant it shall be given in writing, on the informed consent form approved by the Ethics Committee for the specific trial. The informed consent form shall be signed by both the participant and the Investigator. In the consent form there is an explanation to the patient that the information in the patient file, including medical records, will be reviewed only by authorized individuals (e.g. the Ethics Committee, the audit panel of the hospital, the Ministry of Health, representatives of the company responsible for the trial and trial monitoring), while maintaining absolute confidence, and that the patient's identity shall not be disclosed to non-authorized individuals either verbally or in scientific / medical publications.

2.6 Data Protection Issues in Sweden

VGR will comply with the following laws and principles:

1. All aforementioned Europe-based laws and principles.
2. In addition, any clinical trial in Sweden should also be carried out in due compliance with the Swedish Law pertaining to:
 - a. Ethical Reviews on Research regarding Human Subjects (2003:460)
 - b. Swedish collection of statutes: statutes no 2003:615, 2007:1068 and 2007:1069.

3 Ethics

The members of the Consortium declare that the proposal conforms to current legislation and regulations in the countries where the research will be carried out. Moreover, the proposal conforms to relevant EU legislation such as:

1. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union;
2. Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association - Declaration of Helsinki) in its latest version;
3. Convention of the Council of Europe on Human Rights and Biomedicine signed in Oviedo on 4 April 1997, and the Additional Protocol on the Prohibition of Cloning Human Beings signed in Paris on 12 January 1998 (Convention of the Council of Europe on Human Rights and Biomedicine);

4. Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data;
5. Directive 2001/20/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use;
6. Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications).
7. Nothing in the proposal stands in conflict with the opinions of the European Group of Advisers on the Ethical Implications of Biotechnology (1991-1997) and the opinions of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New technologies (as from 1998).

3.1 Articles of the Helsinki Declaration with relevance for DECI Project

6. In medical research involving human subjects, the well-being of the individual research subject must take precedence over all other interests.

11. It is the duty of physicians who participate in medical research to protect the life, health, dignity, integrity, right to self-determination, privacy, and confidentiality of personal information of research subjects.

14. The design and performance of each research study involving human subjects must be clearly described in a research protocol. The protocol should contain a statement of the ethical considerations involved and should indicate how the principles in this Declaration have been addressed. The protocol should include information regarding funding, sponsors, institutional affiliations, other potential conflicts of interest, incentives for subjects and provisions for treating and/or compensating subjects who are harmed as a consequence of participation in the research study. The protocol should describe arrangements for post-study access by study subjects to interventions identified as beneficial in the study or access to other appropriate care or benefits.

16. Medical research involving human subjects must be conducted only by individuals with the appropriate scientific training and qualifications. Research on patients or healthy volunteers requires the supervision of a competent and appropriately qualified physician or other health care professional. The responsibility for the protection of research subjects must always rest with the physician or other health care professional and never the research subjects, even though they have given consent.

22. Participation by competent individuals as subjects in medical research must be voluntary. Although it may be appropriate to consult family members or community leaders, no competent individual may be enrolled in a research study unless he or she freely agrees.

23. Every precaution must be taken to protect the privacy of research subjects and the confidentiality of their personal information and to minimize the impact of the study on their physical, mental and social integrity.

24. In medical research involving competent human subjects, each potential subject must be adequately informed of the aims, methods, sources of funding, any possible conflicts of interest, institutional affiliations of the researcher, the anticipated benefits and potential risks of the study and the discomfort it may entail, and any other relevant aspects of the study. The potential subject must be informed of the right to refuse to participate in the study or to withdraw consent to participate at any time without reprisal. Special attention should be given to the specific information needs of individual potential subjects as well as to the methods used to deliver the information. After ensuring that the potential subject has understood the information, the physician or another appropriately qualified individual must then seek the potential subject's freely-given informed consent, preferably in writing. If the consent cannot be expressed in writing, the non-written consent must be formally documented and witnessed.

30. Authors, editors and publishers all have ethical obligations with regard to the publication of the results of research. Authors have a duty to make publicly available the results of their research on human subjects and are accountable for the completeness and accuracy of their reports. They should adhere to accepted guidelines for ethical reporting. Negative and inconclusive as well as positive results should be published or otherwise made publicly available. Sources of funding, institutional affiliations and conflicts of interest should be declared in the publication. Reports of research not in accordance with the principles of this Declaration should not be accepted for publication.

3.2 Informed consent

Overall, the project does not present ethical issues but legal and privacy ones, as all the data are provided directly by patients who are already undergoing care processes, and professionals who have to be aware of the legal and privacy issues and indirectly through measurement's devices. The international laws regarding data protection concerning good data management practices in the entities that process data will be followed during the project. These include the obligation to process data fairly and in a safe and secure manner and to use personal data for explicit and legitimate purposes. National and EU laws also guarantee individual rights, such as the right to be informed when personal data have been processed and the reason for this processing, the right to access the data and if necessary and the right to have the data amended or deleted.

Principles for collecting informed consent from patient will be fully applied and all the activities to record, store and treat personal data will adhere to EU and national privacy laws:

1. Patients will be informed on how their personal data will be treated and will be asked to give their consensus. Please note: the project will not address children or people unable to provide informed consent. However, if patients enrolled should prove a worsening of their condition of mild cognitive impairment, their stay within pilot groups will be discussed within the ethical board. This may involve also their legally authorized representatives. Three types of legally authorized representatives are identified for granting permission for research participation of these individuals.
2. Health care agents, or durable powers of attorney executed while the individual had decision-making capacity, possess the greatest power to make such decisions. Next in line are legal guardians or conservators, who are appointed by a judicial body to make decisions for an individual determined to be incompetent.
3. When describing issues relating to informed consent, it will be necessary to illustrate an appropriate level of ethical sensitivity, and consider issues of insurance, incidental findings and the consequences of leaving the study.
4. To ensure that the information is easy to understand, all written information that is given to patients/subjects has to be proved by experts on “Easy to Read” Guidelines. Participants will get information in a way that is easy to understand. There has to be consent for all activities of each single participant to take part in the project. There will be written information about the usage of all collected data and in particular about the usage of personal or medical data.
5. A cancellation of the participation will be possible at any point and any time without giving a reason.

The representative of each partner inside the Project Coordination Committee of the project will describe and ensure local compliance to the ethical issues, involving all relevant actors of the company if required (risk manager, Ethical Committee, ...) by answering to the Ethical Issues questionnaire (appendix A of this document).

3.3 Local Ethical Committee

As part of the project, personal data of patients might be required to travel across borders inside the EU. As a result, data concerning the citizens of one Member State are sometimes processed in other Member States of the EU. Therefore, as personal data are collected and exchanged more frequently, regulations on data transfers might become necessary and will be implemented and observed in the project. It is stated explicitly that data will be transferred from one partner to another within the EU only after it was made anonymous. This chapter identifies and briefly summarizes the main national specifications and guidance documents in the partner countries. Identification of national guidance documents, legislation and governance bodies in ethics that are relevant for the national

DECI partners in implementing their work. The chapter will address those partner countries, which plan to involve users in the project. All partners are, of course, under the legal obligation to follow any relevant national laws, meaning they should also be aware of which laws apply to their intended work. Despite their different legislations, all partners in the DECI consortium are under the same moral obligation to protect their users' safety and well-being.

The following sub-section gathers local specifications, required for Local Ethical Committees issues in Spain and Italy.

3.3.1 Local Ethical Committees in Spain

The Ethical Committee in the Hospital de Getafe is the regulatory system in the south area of Madrid. The Ethical Committee in Getafe performs meetings the first week of every month and the results of the meetings and considerations are reported in maximum two weeks.

Any activity within the DECI project that involves the participation of patients, including the research protocol, must be submitted for consideration, guidance and approval to the concerned research ethics committee before the trial begins or the interviews with subjects or caregiver. Information that should be submitted include: "Participant information and consent form" document, a document with the list of investigators, the insurance documents, and so on. The committee has the right to monitor on-going studies. The researcher must provide monitoring information to the committee. The committee can make no amendment to the protocol without consideration and approval. After the end of the study, the researchers must submit a final report to the committee containing a summary of the study's findings and conclusions.

In the DECI Project, it is important to consider serious adverse events that may arise from the intervention. The serious adverse events in clinical trials are defined to include: death, a life-threatening adverse experience, inpatient hospitalization, a persistent or significant disability/incapacity, or a clinically significant laboratory or clinical test result. Important medical events that may not result in death, be life threatening, or require hospitalization may be considered serious adverse experiences if they might jeopardize the participant or might require medical or surgical intervention to prevent one of the outcomes in the definition. An example of this in DECI is an injurious fall resulting in a fracture that occurred during walking or performing exercises with the use of the technological devices.

3.3.2 Local Ethical Committee in Italy

The Ethical Committee of Fondazione Don Gnocchi, acknowledge by the Italian Ministry of Health, has similar rules to the one of Getafe Hospital in Spain. The committee meets approximately every two months. The official feedback of analyzed studies are given in maximum two weeks.

Any activity within the DECI project that involves the participation of patients in Italy must be submitted for consideration and approval to the ethical committee before the

trials begin. Information that should be submitted include among others: "the protocol of the study" a "Participant information and consent form" document, a document with the list of partners and investigators, the "case report form", the insurance documents, and so on. The committee has the right to monitor on-going studies. The researcher must provide monitoring information to the committee. Any major modification to the protocol must be re-submitted for approval by the ethical committee. After the end of the study, the researchers must submit a final report to the committee containing a summary of the study's findings and conclusions.

3.4 Partner needs related to ethics

This section gathers regional-specific information related to ethics management and related Partners needs and issues. The information included in this section is to be intended as a collection of regional specifications.

As this is a living document, this section will in case of provision of additional guidelines for specific countries.

3.4.1 Partners needs related to ethics in Spain

In Spain, the regulation of the personal data is governed by the law of Data Protection Act number 15/1999 (December 13th) adapted to the European directives by the Royal Decree 1720/2007 promulgated on December 21st 2007.

The Data on Health are described in Article 8. Without prejudice to the provisions of Article 11 on assignment, public and private health-care institutions and centres and the corresponding professionals may process personal data relating to the health of persons consulting them or admitted for treatment, in accordance with the provisions of the central or regional government legislation on health care.

3.4.2 Partners needs related to ethics in Israel

According to the Israeli MOH procedures, handling new applications for special clinical trial by the medical institution is done as follows:

The Principal Investigator submits the scientific studies/ clinical trial application to the institutional Ethics Committee. The Ethics Committee review the scientific studies/ clinical trial application and decides whether to approve or reject the application. The Ethics Committee also decides, whether the director of the medical institution is authorized to approve the scientific studies, or whether additional approval by the Ministry of Health is required.

The Ethics Committee shall forward to the director of the medical institution its decisions regarding applications for scientific studies which it has approved and which the Director is authorized to approve without additional approval by the Ministry of Health. The Director shall issue an approval for the scientific studies to the Principal Investigator, detailing the terms and conditions). The Investigator may initiate the scientific studies only after receipt of said approval.

3.4.3 Partners needs related to ethics in Sweden

The Principal Investigator submits the clinical trial application to the institutional Ethics Committee (in this case, the Regional Ethics committee in Gothenburg). The Ethics Committee reviews the clinical trial application or request for amendments therein and decides whether to approve or reject the application.

The Ethics Committee may in addition decide if there is also a need for an application to another agency like the Medical Products Agency when investigational drugs will be used, and in some cases also for medical devices. If there is a need for an application to other agencies like the Medical Products Agency, separate applications have to be made to these agencies for approval.

As a rule, one of the members of the Ethics Committee performs an in-depth reading of the application and the application is then discussed at a formal meeting of the Ethical Committee. Then a decision is sent to the Principal Investigator including comments regarding ethical aspects of the study. In some (most) cases, the Principal Investigator needs to submit a response to the Ethical Committee regarding these comments before the Ethical Committee can approve the study.

The Investigator may initiate the clinical trial only after receipt of approval from the Ethical Committee (and if appropriate; other agencies). The committee meets every month. Typically, the lead-time for getting approval of an application varies between three and six months.

3.4.4 Partners needs related to ethics in Italy

As described above any activity within the DECI project that involves the participation of patients in Italy must be submitted for consideration and approval to a Local Ethical Committee. The activities related to the Italian Pilot site will be therefore submitted to FDG Ethical Committee.

3.5 Emerging issues identified by partners

For the ethics issues a valuable role will be played by the Scientific Advisory Board, leveraging the experience in European and national regulatory frameworks and in other research project of prominent members, at strategic level, of consortium organizations and health organizations, which have endorsed the project.

This section includes additional emerging issues identified by Partners, according to local perspectives.

As this is a living document, further emerging issues might be added at a later stage.

3.5.1 Data protection issues in Spain

As to the project will directly involve subjects suffering from cognitive decline, a caregiver will be identified and, consequently, the informed consent form will be signed by the subject and by the caregiver. Informed consent for legally incompetent subject will be managed in accordance with the National regulations, updated to their most recent version.

As part of the consent process, participants will explicitly asked whether they consent that data collected during the study may continue to be used in the final analysis even if they should lose participation capability whilst the study is ongoing.

4 Appendix A: Ethical Issues Questionnaire

Project partner:

Questionnaire prepared by:

Date:

These tasks/questions apply to all partners that plan any kind of user involvement within the DECI project.

Ethical clearance

1. Do you involve non-researchers (i.e., older persons, family carers, professional careers etc.) in your research work within DECI?
2. Contact relevant bodies to clarify need for ethical clearance for the user involvement within DECI and more specifically find out:
 - a. Do your foreseen research activities need clearance from an ethics committee?
 - b. When do the foreseen activities take place? (for example, Project Month 15/WP)
 - c. Name of ethics committee to contact? Contact person?
 - d. Find out about meeting schedules and deadlines (for example, meetings once a month)
3. Which are the policies about patient privacy and the procedures enforced in the organization for safely managing patient data (informed consent, data protection, patient data anonymization and use for clinical research)?
4. Which are the principles that will be applied for collecting informed consent from patient for their data?
5. How are patients enrolled into trial?

Ethical advisory board

Please send the ethical manager the name(s) of your candidate(s) for the Ethical Advisory Board.

National documents relevant for DECI

Please send the links/names of any national documents (guidelines, legislation, opinions of national bodies etc.) that you think you will need to refer to in involving users in the DECI activities.

Aspects to focus on for each Partner

1. Regional Healthcare Authorities/Networks should focus on these aspects:
 - a. Patient privacy;
 - b. Procedures enforced in the organization and in the network for safely managing patient data;
 - c. Procedures enforced to collect patient consent for transmission within the network.

2. ICT partners should focus on these aspects:
 - a. Patient privacy;
 - b. Security and safe patient data management.

5 Appendix B: List of documents to submit to Ethics Committees

The special form for ethical applications

This form includes detailed information of study rationale and procedures, number of study participants and how they will be selected and included, risk analysis for study participation in terms of ethical and other aspects, safety evaluation of the study procedures, storage of biological tissues if relevant, and how obtained data will be kept and used. It should also be stated whether it is single-centre or multi-centre research and if there are sponsors and if so, which access and rights the sponsor has in terms of collected data.

Study protocol

Background, rationale, study participants, methodology and endpoints should be given as well as statements regarding how data will be kept and rights of the included participants.

Written information and informed consent form

All formal written information to patients (and if appropriate; controls) as well as written informed consent form must be submitted to the Ethical Committee for approval.

Questionnaires and test protocols

All questionnaires and test protocols used should be submitted to the Ethical Committee.

Signed letter from head of clinical institution

The head of the clinical institution where the research will be performed need to state that the research can be performed at the institution.

Other documents

Other documents could be submitted, like a study protocol for laymen.